

Military Communications Satellite System Multiplies UHF Channel Capacity for Mobile Users

Donald v. Z. Wadsworth
Naval Postgraduate School
IEEE Conference Publishing
445 Hoes Lane
Piscataway, NJ 08855-1331

Abstract-The Mobile User Objective System (MUOS) will be the successor to the Navy's UFO satellite communications system. One MUOS proposal relies on a constellation of GEO spacecraft that uses non-processing repeaters and multiple spotbeams for worldwide earth-coverage. UHF frequency reuse greatly increases the number of narrowband voice/data channels available to mobile units. A key design element is the large antenna reflector with an area of 1250 square meters.

I. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the results of a Mobile User Objective System (MUOS) design study for the successor to the Navy's current UFO (UHF Follow-on) satellite communications system. The proposed MUOS design more than doubles DoD-owned, UHF voiceband communications capacity in high-density conflict zones and worldwide. Frequency reuse in the military UHF band is obtained by means of a 40-meter diameter antenna reflector that supports 127 independent earth-coverage spotbeams. The satellite constellation consists of four primary and one or more relocatable GEO (geostationary earth orbit) spacecraft. The latter serve as spares and can extend urban warfare coverage to higher latitudes, using efficient ion propulsion to relocate. The design fully supports current "legacy" terminals/networks, including DAMA (demand assignment multiple access) and DASA (demand assignment single access) operational modes.

The proposed Mobile User (MU) spacecraft repeater is described as "non-processing", although it could perform certain control functions onboard, including call routing, channelization, inter-beam switching, and user-tracking for inter-cell roaming. Whether the order wire functions should continue to be embedded in the DAMA-TDMA frames or assigned to a common channel per beam is an unresolved issue that will impact the design. The MU system could be designed to dynamically accommodate both narrowband voice (up to 9.6 kbps) and wider channels (up to 64 kbps) under DAMA control.

If a processing repeater is implemented, it would be feasible to directly support UHF cellphones that are interoperable with legacy military terminals. This approach may not be economically attractive, since the

ITU (International Telecommunications Union) interference rule would limit the number of cellphones to a dozen or so units per spotbeam cell or high-density conflict zone. The alternative for cellphone users, reliance on evolving commercial L and S-band systems [1], simplifies the MU system design, since the repeater can be non-processing. Although the MU system design presented in this report is based on an array of independent spotbeams, an alternative approach could employ an active phased array with digital beam forming to create the spotbeam cells [2].

II. MISSION NEED

The MUOS study proposal [3] calls for a constellation of military communications spacecraft that will provide mobile users, including cellphone-like handheld terminals, with a much-needed expansion in assured-access, secure, narrowband voice/data communications capacity. Such a global-coverage constellation, supporting both peacetime and contingency crisis military operations, would supersede the current UFO system of 8 primary and one in-orbit spare S/C (spacecraft) approaching end of life in the 2007-2010 timeframe. This future DoD-controlled constellation of Mobile User spacecraft must support numerous "legacy" (e.g., AN/WSC-3 and SPITFIRE) UHF tactical terminals and their networks that still will be in service beyond the 2007 date. To assure a smooth transition, the MU system must be able to operate simultaneously with remaining legacy UFO spacecraft.

Advantages of the UHF bands, apart from compatibility with a large military user base, are significant foliage penetration compared to higher bands, such as used for commercial cellular systems (e.g., GSM and IS-95), and minimal rain attenuation. Disadvantages are increased manmade interference and ionospheric fading, compared to higher bands.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

A. Frequency Reuse Increases Capacity

As proposed in this paper, one approach for increasing communications capacity is to reuse the allocated UFO orbital slots and authorized satellite communications (SATCOM) military band (243-318 MHz) rather than to acquire new allocations for the MU system [4]. Frequency

This study was sponsored by the Dept. of the Navy, SPAWAR, PEO-SCS/PMW 146.

reuse must be on a non-interference basis with current military and other NTIA/ITU authorized users. The global frequency plan for the UFO-UHF system channels, together with some FLTSAT channels, falls in the 243270 MHz (downlink) and 293318 MHz (uplink) bands. The UFO frequency plans provide 84 separate 5-kHz channels and 68 separate 25-kHz channels. These are usually spaced at 10 kHz and 50 kHz intervals, resp., in order to provide guardbands. Each channel requires an uplink and a downlink that are separated in frequency. Additionally, four downlink 25-kHz channel frequencies are assigned to fleet broadcast service, only 2 of these being available in a single-coverage region..

Due to TDMA (time division multiple access), each 25-kHz channel is roughly equivalent in capacity to five 5-kHz channels. Each 5-kHz-equivalent channel can support various services, such as 4.8 kbps half-duplex, 2.4 kbps full-duplex, or 2.4 kbps half-duplex with 1/2 rate FEC coding. Omitting the broadcast channels, the UFO plan provides a maximum of $4(21+5 \times 17) = 424$ 5-kHz-equivalent channels in an overlap coverage region. In practice, some channels are unavailable, due to interference or malfunction. The fraction of these channels accessible to an earth terminal varies from 50% (single S/C coverage region) to 100% (overlap coverage region between adjacent S/C). The total bandwidth used by the UFO plan, including guardbands and up/down links is about 8.5 MHz.

Fig. 1 shows the northern hemisphere coverage for one of the UFO S/C, within the earth terminal 5° line-of-sight elevation angle. The figure illustrates regions of

overlapping coverage from adjacent S/C which are spaced approximately 90° apart in longitude in GEO. Actually there are two S/C in the vicinity of each orbital slot, although they are treated as one in the figure.

To avoid co-channel interference in the overlap regions, the 5-kHz and 25-kHz channels provided by adjacent S/C (e.g., #1 and #2) are separated in frequency according to plans designated as U and V in Fig.1. In UFO nomenclature, U corresponds to the sum of the UFO P and O plans and V to the sum of the UFO N and Q plans. S/C on opposite sides of the earth access the same plans, since they are not mutually visible. Within the $E = 5^\circ$ elevation angle contour, 58% of the total earth coverage area has access to both plans U and V. As shown in Fig. 2, this dual coverage drops to 16% within the $E = 25^\circ$ contour (urban warfare requirement).

B. Multibeam Antenna More Than Doubles Capacity

Under the MU frequency-reuse system, the UFO S/C's single earth-coverage beam is replaced by a pattern of overlapping narrow spotbeams, each of which provides both the U and V plans. This is accomplished by means of an offset 127-element feed array that forms independent spot beams with the aid of a parabolic-shape reflector. The transmit array elements might be

Fig. 1. UFO spacecraft footprint for elevation angles $E \geq 5$ degrees.

Fig. 2. UFO spacecraft footprint for urban warfare ($E \geq 25$ degrees)

Fig. 3. Spotbeam cell pattern for earth coverage.

short-backfire crossed dipoles, spaced approximately at half wavelengths, resulting in an array diameter of about 6 meters. Receive elements might be capacitively-coupled discs. If transmit and receive array elements were combined in the same space without exceeding PIM (passive intermodulation) and mutual interference requirements, then transmit and receive signals could share the same antenna aperture.

Approximately $1+3n(n+1) = 127$ spotbeam cells are needed to provide edge-of-earth coverage, as illustrated by the hexagonal pattern of Fig. 3 for $n = 6$ bands of cells. The hexagon centers correspond to spotbeam centers. The circumscribed circle for each hexagon is the spotbeam half-power contour. Overlap with an adjacent cell is illustrated for the center cell.

The pattern assures the signal level at any point within a cell will not fall more than 3 dB below the maximum for the cell. A single cell could cover the "high density zone" of a conflict region (800 km by 1000 km). A "greater regional zone" (3000 km X 3000 km) might require up to 9 adjacent cells. The cell half-power footprint diameter d is related to the edge-of-earth coverage diameter D by $D = 1.732nd$ where D and d are the angles subtended at the S/C. For a GEO S/C, $D = 17.9^\circ$, so that for $n = 6$, $d = 1.72^\circ$.

The channel frequencies assigned by the onboard controller to each cell can be reused in other cells, so long as adjacent cells have no common assignments, in order to avoid co-channel interference between beams. Under this arrangement, the cochannel interference level from non-adjacent cells would be at least 13 dB below the desired signal at the cell edge (worst case location), assuming an antenna with a "parabolic" aperture field distribution [5]. This interference level has negligible performance effect.

Within a S/C edge-of-earth coverage region, the available number of simultaneous, half-duplex voice channels under the MU system is more than double that for the UFO system. This is illustrated in Fig. 4 for a 13-cell subset of the 127-cell pattern. Three different frequency groupings are indicated. 324 5-kHz-equivalent voice

Fig. 4. Spotbeam cells provide frequency reuse.

channels (out of a maximum of 424 per cell) could be assigned to the cell covering a high-density zone while simultaneously providing 300 additional, non-interfering channels in the 6 adjacent cells. Within the same coverage subset, an additional 260 voice circuits are split between Battle Groups 1 and 2 (each nominally covering a 500-km diameter area), leaving still another 164 circuits to be assigned to four remaining cells. The total for the 13 cells is 1048 simultaneous 5-kHz-equivalent voice circuits. Frequency reuse in the remaining 114 cells provides further capacity. In contrast, a collocated pair of UFO S/C provides a maximum of 212 circuits in a single-coverage region.

1) *DAMA wideband channel*: Under dynamic DAMA channel management, a temporary imagery channel could be constituted from 50 of the contiguous 5-kHz voice channels and their guardbands within one of the allocated DoD UHF 500-kHz bands. This channel could link the battle groups to the high-density zone. Channels compatible with 56 kbps standards could also be constituted.

2) *Antenna reflector and cell size*: An offset feed array illuminates a parabolic reflector that has a physical aperture area of about 1250 m², equivalent to a 40-m diameter circle, achievable with current technology [6]. For a “parabolic” aperture field amplitude distribution [5], the 3-dB spot beamwidths range from $72.6\lambda/D = 1.71^\circ$ (319 MHz) to 2.24° (244 MHz). The corresponding

circular footprint (cell) diameters at the subsatellite point range from 1100 km to 1500 km, the footprints becoming elongated as the earth terminal is offset from the subsatellite point. Assuming an antenna efficiency $\eta = 55\%$, the midband uplink (306 MHz) and downlink (257 MHz) antenna mainlobe gains are $\eta(\pi D/\lambda)^2 \rightarrow 39.6$ dBi and 38.1 dBi, resp. For a parabolic distribution, assuming the feed is at the focus, the first sidelobe is 24.6 dB below the mainlobe.

C. Relocatable Spacecraft for Urban Warfare

While an elevation angle $E = 5^\circ$ currently guarantees global coverage to 70° latitude, urban warfare global coverage, defined as $E \geq 25^\circ$, is only guaranteed to 40° latitude (the cusps of Fig. 2). Many major cities are located north of 40° . The coverage could be extended to 57° if one of the MU relocatable multibeam S/C were moved to the desired longitude. Ion thruster technology, employed for stationkeeping and initial orbit raising, also makes multiple relocations feasible during a spacecraft lifetime [7].

D. Spacecraft Repeater

Both non-processing and processing repeater designs are options for the MU system. In the former case, the S/C provides call routing, channelization, IF matrix switching, and DAMA-TDMA control for both inter-cell and intra-

cell users. In the processing design, in order to provide interoperability among legacy and cellphones, the S/C additionally performs waveform demodulation/modulation and translation (e.g., from non-spread to spread spectrum signals), FEC (forward error correction) decoding/encoding, de-interleaving/interleaving, and, possibly, decryption/encryption.

1) *Non-processing repeater option:* If cellphone terminals are only supported via surface gateways, then the MU repeaters can be non-processing, simplifying the design. The adjacent S/C onboard controllers need to be inter-linked (directly or via a ground relay) to efficiently share databases and transition mobile users as they roam from one region to another. Users could be tracked by reporting their GPS (global positioning system) positions on the encrypted ROW (return order wire).

In the case of current SATCOM (satellite communications) terminals (e.g., AN/WSC-3 and SPITFIRE), the DAMA-TDMA waveform would not have to be altered. The DAMA control center could still be located on the ground. Although the DAMA order wire is currently included in each channel frame (i.e., in-band), an alternative is to dedicate separate UHF order wire channels to serve each beam. The downlink power for each spotbeam could be designed to adaptively maintain current UFO flux densities at the surface.

2) *Processing repeater option:* For SATCOM links, the low-EIRP (effective isotropic radiated power) and low-G/T (receiver figure of merit) cellphone terminals require the high-gain spotbeams in order to "close" the uplinks and downlinks. To meet the BER (bit error rate) specification with a cellphone, the S/C spotbeam signal output level must be increased $10\log(1.78/0.062) = 14.6$ dB over that for legacy terminals (Table 2), resulting in a surface power flux density (W/m^2) that far exceeds the ITU 6% rule for downlink interference. This rule requires technical coordination between satellite networks if the inband interference from a new or modified network increases the "victim" receiver's system noise temperature by more than 6% or, equivalently, increases the system noise power by $10\log(1.06) = 0.25$ dB.

The solution is to reduce the inband flux density by means of a modulation that spreads the spotbeam signal power over a much wider bandwidth than that of the victim. If spread-spectrum modulation is employed for cellphone downlinks, then cellphones could simultaneously share the spotbeams with legacy terminals, without exceeding the 6% interference rule. The cellphone uplinks also would employ a spread-spectrum waveform to improve performance.

Spread-spectrum waveform design is complicated by the fact that the UHF MILSATCOM (military SATCOM) channels are not always contiguous in frequency, being interspersed among other users. The non-military users account for nearly 20 gaps (totaling 26.5 MHz) in the UFO

uplink/downlink spectrum. These gaps do not include the NATO IV, UK SKYNET 4, FLTSAT, and AFSAT/LEASAT channels. Additionally, there is a 22.8 MHz gap between the UFO uplink/downlink bands. Even where the MILSATCOM channels are contiguous in a 500-kHz band, certain channels may have to be blocked temporarily, depending on the theater of operations. SATCOM "landing rights" may be denied in selected channels because of interference with sovereign-nation channel assignments (e.g., commercial broadcast services).

As described in [8], spread-spectrum possibilities include wideband CDMA (code division multiple access, e.g., the IS-95 standard), FDMA (frequency division multiple access) with narrowband CDMA, and TDFH (time-division frequency hopping, e.g., the GSM standard). In the latter two options, unlike wideband CDMA, strong narrowband interference (e.g., legacy UFO and foreign broadcast station transmissions) can be avoided by omitting these bands from the spread-spectrum waveform.

The spread bandwidth B_{ss} required to meet the 6% rule can be estimated by using the AN/WSC-3 system noise temperature $T_{sys} = 892$ K as a reference. The permissible downlink signal flux density in $B = 25$ kHz is $\Omega_{6\%} = 0.06(kT_{sys}B)/A_e$, Wm^{-2} , where the receive antenna effective area $A_e = G\lambda^2/(4\pi)$ and Boltzmann's constant $k = 1.38E-23$ J/K. The permissible *spectral* flux density, units of Wm^{-2}/Hz , must satisfy $\Omega_{6\%}/B = \Omega/B_{ss}$ where $(\Omega)_{dBWm^{-2}} = -137.6$ from Table 2. For a 300-MHz center frequency ($\lambda = 1$ m), combining these relations, the required spread bandwidth $B_{ss} = B\Omega/\Omega_{6\%} = 23.6$ MHz. For BPSK (binary phase shift keying) modulation, this corresponds to a "processing gain" of 23600/25 or 30 dB.

E. Downlink EIRP Constraint

A UFO transponder with a 26-dBW EIRP operating on an allocated 25-kHz UHF channel produces a surface power flux density of -152.2 dBWm $^{-2}$ or, equivalently, -108.2 dBWm $^{-2}Hz^{-1}$, in a plane normal to the direction of propagation. This value, based on a path distance of 40,710 km and a propagation/miscellaneous loss margin of $(L_m)_{dB} = 15$ -dB for the stress scenario, serves as a benchmark for specifying the MU spotbeam flux density Ω required to support legacy terminals, as indicated in Tables 1 and 2.

IV. SYSTEM PERFORMANCE

The link performances for three terminals, the shipboard AN/WSC-3 with the OE-82C Antenna Group, the SPITFIRE man-portable terminal, and a future 1-watt UHF cellphone terminal are compared in Tables 1 and 2. Table 1 is based on the current UFO repeater while Table 2 is based on the proposed MU multiple spotbeam repeater. In both tables, the UFO and MU repeaters are conservatively

modeled as non-processing, which slightly underestimates noise performance as compared to a processing repeater. Sources for parameter values given in the tables are indicated by the references.

A DAMA-TDMA waveform in a BPSK 25-kHz channel with a 19.2 burst rate and an $R_b = 9.6$ kbps information rate is modeled. The required value of the E_b/n_o (bit energy to noise power density ratio) parameter, corresponding to a 10^{-5} BER, is 4.6 dB, based on FEC convolutional coding with rate $1/2$, constraint length $K = 7$ encoding, 3-bit quantization Viterbi decoding, and interleaving. For the comparison, representative UFO channel frequencies of $f_{up} = 306$ MHz and $f_{dn} = 257$ MHz were chosen. The modeled slant range $d = 40,710$ km corresponds to complete $\pm 65^\circ$ latitude coverage ($E = 8.8^\circ$ minimum line-of-sight elevation angle to S/C). The repeater antenna gains listed are maximum values; the reduction in gain at locations off beam center is the "contour" loss, amounting to 3 dB for the half-power contour.

The same stress scenario is incorporated into both tables. It consists of uplink and downlink manmade interference plus 15-dB uplink and downlink margins, L_m , for fading and miscellaneous losses (propagation, ionospheric fading, modulation implementation, contour, multipath, foliage). In the tables, the uplink carrier-to-noise power density ratio was calculated from

$$(C/n_o)_{up} = (EIRP)(G/T_{sys})/(k L_{fs} L_m)$$

with a similar expression for the downlink. The quantity L_{fs} is known as the "free space loss." The carrier-to-(total noise+interference) power density ratio at the receive earth terminal is

$$(C/n_o)_{tot} = 1/\{1/(C/n_o)_{up} + 1/(C/n_o)_{dn} + 1/(C/I_o)\}.$$

A. Link Performance Based on UFO Repeater

Assuming the current UFO repeater, the channel EIRP is modeled as 26 dBW. As Table 1 indicates, SPITFIRE requires a 6.2 dB increase in E_b/n_o in order to meet the BER specification under the stress scenario, while the AN/WSC-3 still has a comfortable 3.9 dB margin. The 9.6 kbps cellphone links would require an increase of $14.6 + 4.6 = 19.2$ dB in E_b/n_o .

B. Link Performance Based on Spotbeam Repeater

In Table 2, the performances for the three terminals are also based on a 25-kHz channel and the same stress scenario as in Table 1, but the MU spotbeam repeater replaces the UFO repeater. The uplink carrier/interference ratios are improved by 6 dB, due to the narrow spotbeams. The channel EIRP remains at 26 dBW for legacy terminal downlinks but is increased to 40.6 dBW for cellphones, to compensate for smaller terminal antenna gain and the corresponding increase in manmade interference. Under these conditions, the achievable E_b/n_o for the cellphone is

4.9 dB, slightly exceeding the requirement. SPITFIRE misses the requirement by 1.8 dB, which is still 4.9 dB better than can be achieved with the UFO repeater. The AN/WSC-3 retains the 3.9 dB margin.

C. Manmade Uplink Interference Model

Manmade uplink interference is modeled as AWGN (additive white gaussian noise) in the link performance equation while manmade downlink interference is modeled as an additive term in the receiver system equivalent noise-source temperature. [3] provides a probability density distribution for the effective interference EIRP level of UHF surface emitters, as integrated by a GEO earth-coverage uplink beam (17.4° beamwidth). The worst tenth-percentile for manmade uplink UHF interference in a 2.1 kHz corresponds to an emitter EIRP ≥ 24 dBm. The 24 dBm value is used for the stress scenario. Assuming a uniform spectral density distribution and no propagation losses other than spherical spreading, this translates to an interference flux density at the S/C of $24 - 30 - 163.2 + 10\log(25/2.1) = -158.4$ dBWm⁻² in a 25-kHz bandwidth. For a 2.14° spotbeam, the uplink interference level for the stress scenario is reduced to

$$-158.4 + 20\log(2.14/17.4) = -176.7 \text{ dBWm}^{-2},$$

assuming a uniform surface distribution of emitters.

The spotbeam uplink signal-to-interference power ratio, C/I , that is exceeded less than 10% of the time depends on the ratio of uplink signal and interference power flux densities, Ω and Ω_{int} , resp.: $(C/I)_{dB} = (\Omega/\Omega_{int})_{dB} + \Delta_{corr}$ where $(\Omega_{int})_{dBWm^{-2}} = -176.7$. $\Delta_{corr} = 6$ dB (nominal value) is a correction term that accounts for the fact that part of the $(L_m)_{dB} = 15$ -dB uplink signal loss margin includes deep ionospheric fading, whereas the uplink interference model omits propagation losses including fading. For a narrow spotbeam, ionospheric fading loss for both signal and interference is expected to be partially correlated. To illustrate, since $I = I_o B$ where I_o is the average interference power spectral density (WHz⁻¹) in the bandwidth $B = 25$ kHz, the cellphone Table 2 entry $(C/I_o)_{dBHz} = (C/I)_{dB} + 10\log 25000 = -177.4 + 176.7 + 6 + 44 = 49.3$ dBHz, where the cellphone uplink signal flux density $(\Omega)_{dBWm^{-2}} = -177.4$.

D. Manmade Downlink Interference Model

The equivalent noise-source temperature for manmade downlink interference, modeled at the receive antenna port is denoted by T_{int} . [3] gives $T_{int} = 645$ K for a hemispheric-pattern antenna. In Table 1, this is scaled to the antenna pattern, being reduced by a factor of 4 for the SPITFIRE antenna and by 8 for the higher gain AN/WSC-3 antenna. This interference is not correlated with ionospheric fading.

E. Earth Terminal G/T

The system noise temperature computed at the terminal antenna port is $T_{\text{sys}} = T_{\text{sky}} + T_{\text{int}} + LT_r + (L-1)T_p$ where $L > 1$ denotes the loss factor due to the antenna feed and T_p is its physical temperature, taken as 290 K. T_r is the receiver's equivalent noise-source temperature at the LNA (low noise amplifier) input. The AN/WSC-3, SPITFIRE, and cellphone receivers have system noise temperatures of 892 K, 1028 K, and 1512 K, resp., based on a conservative value of 300 K for sky noise [3] and the T_{int} values of Table 1. The cellphone antenna gain is specified as 0 dBi.

F. Number of Users per Cell

If the ITU 6% rule is to be met for the AN/WSC-3 as a representative "victim" receiver, then each UHF cellphone within a spotbeam requires 23.6 MHz of uplink bandwidth, as previously determined for an unspread bandwidth of 25 kHz. Assuming the same bandwidth for the downlink and that $318-243 = 75$ MHz of UHF bandwidth is available, only $75/46.2$ or (rounding down) one half-duplex, 9.6 kbps cellphone can be accommodated per beam. This number is increased to 5 cellphones if 5-kHz-equivalent unspread bandwidth channels (2.4 kbps full-duplex service with no FEC) are used. If the interference environment permits the uplink spread-spectrum processing gain to be reduced, thus freeing bandwidth, then the number of cellphones per cell might be increased by a factor of 2. Commercial alternatives for cellphones (e.g., Iridium, Globalstar, ICO) are evaluated in [1].

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This design study is the result of a team effort by the author and several Naval Postgraduate School students, including MAJ Jon Cook, LT Joel Hicks, and Capt Steve Paxton. Valuable guidance was obtained from PMW 146, the Naval Space Command (especially W. Shumadine), and the Aerospace Corporation.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. G. B. Paxton, "A Scenario-Based Analysis of the Mobile Satellite Services", Naval Postgraduate School Master's Thesis, June 1999.
- [2] N. M. Homan, "A Military UHF Communications Satellite Design for the User On-the-Move", Naval Postgraduate School Master's Thesis, December 1997.
- [3] "MUOS Performance Specification for Concept Exploration", 1999.
- [4] J. P. Cook, "Joint Spectrum Acquisition and Management for the 21st Century", Naval Postgraduate School Master's Thesis, June 1999.
- [5] M. Skolnik, *Introduction to Radar Systems*, 2nd ed, McGraw-Hill, 1980.
- [6] D. v. Z. Wadsworth, Naval Postgraduate School Memorandum, 1999, unpublished.
- [7] J. T. Hicks, Naval Postgraduate School Memorandum, 1999, unpublished.
- [8] T. S. Rapport, *Wireless Communications*, Prentice-Hall, 1996.
- [9] *NAVY UHF Satellite Communication Description*, NOSC, FSCS-200-83-1, 31 December 1991.
- [10] "Prime Item Product Specification for the Satellite Communications DAMA Manpack Terminal, AN/PSC-5", U.S. Army CECOM, 17 July 1996.
- [11] W. Shumadine, "Naval SATCOM Systems and Applications", Course SS-4900, Naval Postgraduate School, October 1997.
- [12] "Contract Specifications for UFO Satellite System", SPAWAR-S-746, 26 April 1988.
- [13] MIL-STD-C28838C(EC).
- [14] Contractor Document, Hughes Aircraft Co., 1988.

TABLE 1. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON (UFO REPEATER)

PARAMETERS ch bandwidth = 25kHz burst rate = 19.2 kbps uncoded rate $R_b = 9.6$ kbps	units for tabulated values	UFO earth-coverage repeater	AN/WSC-3 shipboard terminal	AN/PSC-5 SPITFIRE terminal	MU cellphone
		DOWNLINK xmt (254 MHz)	UPLINK xmt (305MHz)	UPLINK xmt (305MHz)	UPLINK xmt (305MHz)
P (HPA output)/(feed loss)	W	8.5	100 [9]	18 [10]	1.2 (spec.)
G (ant. gain)	dBi	18.7 [14]	12 [9]	6 [10]	0 (spec.)
EIRP = P G	dBW	26 [9]	32	18.6	0.8
$\Omega = EIRP/(4\pi d^2 L_m)$	dBWm ⁻²	-152.2	-146.2	-159.6	-177.4
$L_{fs} = (4\pi f d/c)^2$	dB	172.8	174.3	174.3	174.3
$(C/n_o)_{up}; L_m(dB)=15$	dBHz		55.3	41.9	25.6
$(C/I_o)_{up}; \Delta_{corr} = 0$ dB	dBHz		56.2	42.8	43.3
		UPLINK rcv (305MHz)	DOWNLINK rcv (254MHz)	DOWNLINK rcv (254MHz)	DOWNLINK rcv (254MHz)
NF (LNA/preamp input)	dB	6.3 (est.)	3.7 [13]	4 dB [10]	4 dB (spec.)
L (feed/diplexer loss)	dB	0.5 (est.)	0.7 (est.)	0.7 (est.)	0.7 (spec.)
T_{sky}	K	300 [3]	300 [3]	300 [3]	300 [10]
T_{int}	K	0	645/8	645/4	645 [10]
T_{sys}	K	1413 (derived)	892	1028	1512
G (ant. gain)	dBi	15.5 [14]	11 [9]	6 [10]	0 (spec.)
G/T_{sys}	dBK ⁻¹	-16.0 [11,12]	-18.5	-24.1	-31.8
$L_{fs} = (4\pi f d/c)^2$	dB	174.3	172.8	172.8	172.8
$(C/n_o)_{dn}; L_m(dB)=15$	dBHz		50.3	44.7	37.0
$(C/n_o)_{tot}$	dBHz		48.3	38.2	25.2
$E_b/n_o = (C/n_o)_{tot}/R_b$	dB		8.5	-1.6	-14.6
$(E_b/n_o)_{req}; 10^{-5}$ BER	dB		4.6 (Q=3 bits)	4.6 (Q=3 bits)	4.6 (Q=3 bits)

TABLE 2. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON (SPOTBEAM REPEATER)

PARAMETERS ch bandwidth = 25kHz burst rate = 19.2 kbps uncoded rate $R_b = 9.6$ kbps	units for tabulated values	MU spotbeam repeater	AN/WSC-3 shipboard terminal	AN/PSC-5 SPITFIRE terminal	MU cellphone
		DOWNLINK xmt (257 MHz)	UPLINK xmt (306MHz)	UPLINK xmt (306MHz)	UPLINK xmt (306MHz)
P (HPA output)/(feed loss)	W	0.062 (1.78)	100 [9]	18 [10]	1.2 (spec.)
G (ant. gain)	dBi	38.1 (spec.)	12 [9]	6 [10]	0 (spec.)
EIRP = P G	dBW	26.0 (40.6)	32.0	18.6	0.8
$\Omega = EIRP/(4\pi d^2 L_m)$	dBWm ⁻²	-152.2 (-137.6)	-146.2	-159.6	-177.4
$L_{fs} = (4\pi f d/c)^2$	dB	172.8	174.3	174.3	174.3
$(C/n_o)_{up}; L_m(dB)=15$	dBHz		79.4	66.0	49.6
$(C/I_o)_{up}; \Delta_{corr} = 6$ dB	dBHz		79.1	65.7	49.3
		UPLINK rcv (306MHz)	DOWNLINK rcv (257MHz)	DOWNLINK rcv (257MHz)	DOWNLINK rcv (257MHz)
NF (LNA/preamp input)	dB		3.7 [13]	4 dB [10]	4 dB (spec.)
L (feed/diplexer loss)	dB		0.7 (est.)	0.7 (est.)	0.7 (spec.)
T_{sky}	K	300 [3]	300 [3]	300 [3]	300 [3]
T_{int}	K	0	645/8	645/4	645 [3]
T_{sys}	K	1413	892	1028	1512
G (ant. gain)	dBi	39.6 (spec.)	11 [9]	6 [10]	0 (spec.)
G/T_{sys}	dBK ⁻¹	8.1	-18.5	-24.1	-31.8
$L_{fs} = (4\pi f d/c)^2$	dB	174.3	172.8	172.8	172.8
$(C/n_o)_{dn}; L_m(dB)=15$	dBHz		48.3	42.7	49.6
$(C/n_o)_{tot}$	dBHz		48.3	42.7	44.7
$E_b/n_o = (C/n_o)_{tot}/R_b$	dB		8.5	2.8	4.9
$(E_b/n_o)_{req}; 10^{-5}$ BER	dB		4.6 (Q=3 bits)	4.6 (Q=3 bits)	4.6 (Q=3 bits)

Note: values in parentheses are required to close downlink for cellphone.